

WWLLN

World Wide Lightning Location Network

WWLLN is a research collaboration among >50 universities and government labs, managed by the University of Washington, to locate lightning in real time everywhere in the world. All operations are covered by faculty salaries and data sales (no government or private funding). See <http://wwlln.net>

Technique: VLF (Very Low Frequency) radio receivers detect lightning-generated sferics, identify the wave packet time of group arrival (TOGA), TOGAs are then used to calculate source stroke location). WWLLN provides the location and time as well as other parameters of each stroke such as the radiated VLF energy ⁽²⁾

Coverage: Global (receivers on every continent, including 5 in Antarctica)

Resolution:

Spatial Accuracy: 4.3 km (mean), 3.0 km (Median), tail to 10 km. ⁽³⁾

Time Accuracy: <2 microseconds (have been used to correct two different satellite clocks)

Stroke Detection efficiency:

Strokes over 40 kA peak current: ~70-80% ⁽⁴⁾

All cloud to ground strokes: 15 to 25%

All In-cloud strokes: ~5%

Relative Detection Efficiency:

Global, hourly, 1x1 degree grid adjustment values provided as if WWLLN had the same detection efficiency everywhere ⁽⁵⁾

Thunderstorm Detection Efficiency:

>90% of all global thunderstorms located on synoptic 3-hour time scale (since 2006 ⁽⁶⁾)

Average Strokes located/day: >800,000 strokes/day

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WWLLN Technical References:

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